

POLYNANOBARRIER PROPERTIES OF CRUDE OIL
A. M. Pashayev*, R. A. Dashdiyev, Yang Sheng Jun***,**
Lyu Bin**, Shi Ping*****, N. J. Dashdiyeva***** &**
T. K. Dashdiyeva*****

* Academician of ANAS, Rector of the National Aviation Academy of Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan

** Academician of EANS, Deputy director of Oil Service Company "Black Stone" Co., Ltd, Azerbaijan

*** Exploration and Development Department Manager of Sinopec International Petroleum E&P Corporation, "Kazakhstan", China

**** Senior Engineer of Sinopec International Petroleum E&P Corporation, "Kazakhstan", China

***** Chief engineer of Oil Service Company "Black Stone" Co., Ltd, China

***** Candidate of Technical Sciences, Consultant of Oil Service Company "Black Stone" Co., Ltd, Azerbaijan

***** Doctoral Student of the Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry, Baku, Azerbaijan

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Abstract:

The article is a priority publication of a potential scientific discovery with the formula: a previously unknown polynanobarrier property of crude oil has been theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanosized dispersed phase, nanomolecular - adsorption layers (NMAL) around the dispersed phase globules, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure. Experimental confirmation of the unknown polynanobarrier properties of crude oil was carried out by the authors by purposeful selection of some oil fields in the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as samples of numerous demulsifiers from leading companies in the world.

Key Words: polynanobarrierproperty of crude oil, fourfold nanostructure of oil, demulsifiers with a polynanostructure, desuspensers, complex interaction of oxyalkylene block copolymers simultaneously with hydrophilic and hydrophobic phases of oil emulsions, the property of inhibiting the formation of ultra-stable hard destructible water-oil emulsions, suspensions (HDWOE, HDWOS) and viscoelastic systems (VES).

1. Introduction:

At each field, the produced fluid in production wells consists of a mixture of oil + formation water + mechanical impurities + gas [1-10]. According to scientists and specialists in reservoir conditions due to the absence of dispersion processes of liquid components, emulsions are not formed [3-5]. Emulsions of three known types (reverse emulsion: water in oil W / O; direct emulsion: oil in water N / W; multiple or medium emulsion: W / N / W [3, 24], in subsequent texts we can limit yourself by term "average emulsion") are formed in the conditions of production wells [5-10]. Emulsions of the B / N / B type in oilfield practice are called intermediate layers or HDWOE. At the same time, the possibility of the formation of hard destructible water-oil suspensions (HDWOS) was left without attention. In our opinion, HDWOEare formed in a mixture with HDWOS [24]. This phenomenon is more significantly and visually manifested in oil wells in the initial period of oil field operation (immediately after the stage of well development, when the residues of drilling fluids, especially solid dispersed particles of bentonite clay form HDWOS), as well as in the later stages of oil field operation, when HDWOS are formed in wells with the help of solid particles of partially destroyed formation rocks (clay, carbonates, quartz sand, etc.) [24]. Natural oil emulsions, oil nanocolloids, {catch oil; granary oil; bottom sediments of technological and commercial tanks; oil sludge; gas hydrates; polymer-containing oil emulsions; viscous-elastic oil emulsions (we have established for the first time that viscous-elastic oil emulsions, which are formed under conditions of primary preparation of oil (PPO) in some fields, for example, "Uzen", "Tenge Oil & Gas", oil and gas production department (OGPD) "Jaikmunayqaz" JSC "Embamunayqaz", etc. are capable of absorbing petroleum gases, water, oil, solid particles of organic and inorganic systems were first named colloidal barns [11, 12]} including HDWOE and HDWOS can have a fourfold nanostructure:nanomicellar structure of the dispersion medium [13-17];nanoscale fractions of the dispersed phase; nanosized molecular adsorption layers (NMAL) or protective shells or "armor" shells (from a scientific point of view, NMAL would be more correct); organic nanoparticles (based on paraffins, ceresins, porphyrins, carbon compounds such as carbenes, carbides, organometallic and organosilicon compounds) and inorganic origin (based on clay, iron sulfides, salts, particles of stratal rocks) inside of NMAL [11, 12, 18-24].Thus, in our opinion, there exists, in our opinion, a previously unknown polynanobarrier property of crude oil due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an

internal nanomedium, due to the nanosized dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the dispersed globules phases, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure (conventional demulsifiers). Primary theoretical reports on the existence of a nanobarrier structure in crude oil were noted in a localized form by the authors in [11, 20-24]. Consequently, the experimental confirmation of the objectivity of the existence of the polynanobarrier properties of crude oil can be direct evidence of the corresponding project of scientific discovery.

2. Objects and Methods of Research:

Research Objects:

Samples of crude oil from various oil fields of the Republic of Kazakhstan (RK), as well as samples of numerous demulsifiers from leading companies in the world were used as objects of research.

Crude Oil from Various Fields:

Crude oil from the "Uzen" field of "Ozenmunaigas" JSC. Required information on the field and forecasts regarding the polynanobarrier properties of crude oil (PNBPCO): the field has been in operation since 1965; the annual oil production is 5.5 million tons; stable oil emulsion; viscosity at 40°C 30-40 mPa·s; oil density $\rho = 844-874 \text{ kg / m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type: "average" oil [25]); water cut up to 98%; paraffins ~25%; resins ~15%; asphaltenes on average 3%; oil pour point $T_{pp} = 30-32^\circ\text{C}$ [6, 7]. Predictions for PNBPCO: expected the manifestation of PNBPCO at all of the above levels of the polynanostructures of the system due to the nanostructure of the dispersion medium as the external phase, and as the internal medium of the nanoscale dispersed phase, NMAL around the globules of the dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside the NMAL, which together reduce the efficiency the action of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure (conventional demulsifiers).

Crude oil from the "Zhetybai" field of "Mangistaumunaigas" JSC. Required information on the field and forecasts regarding the PNBPCO: the field has been in operation since 1967; the annual oil production is 1.1 million tons; stable oil emulsion; oil density $\rho = 830-870 \text{ kg / m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type: "average" oil [25]); water cut up to 98%; paraffins ~25-28%; resins up to 15%; asphaltenes on average 3.4%; oil pour point $T_{pp} = 30-32^\circ\text{C}$ [8, 9]. Predictions for PNBPCO: expected: manifestation of PNBPCO at all the above levels of the nanostructures of the system due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, NMAL around the globules of the dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure (conventional demulsifiers).

Crude oil from field of "Zhalgiztobemunai" DLLP. Required information on the field and forecasts regarding the PNBPCO: the field has been in operation since 2003; the annual volume of oil production is ~182,000 tons; highly resistant oil emulsion; oil density $\rho \approx 940 \text{ kg / m}^3$ (by density it belongs to the type: "heavy" oil [25]); water cut up to ~32%; paraffins ~1.8%; resins up to ~15%; asphaltenes 5.0-5.5%, on average 5.25% [26]. Predictions for PNBPCO, expected: manifestation of PNBPCO: at all the above levels of the system nanostructures due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, NMAL around the dispersed phase globules, nanoparticles inside the NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure (conventional demulsifiers).

Crude oil from the "Akkulka" field of TethysAralGaz LLP. Required information on the field and forecasts regarding the PNBPCO: the field has been in operation since 2011; the annual oil production is ~255,000 tons; oil emulsion is not stable and refers to a mixture of a macroemulsion and a coarsely dispersed system, which are easily destroyed during thermochemical treatment with the help of demulsifiers; there is a weak asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase; there are no nanoscale dispersed phase, NMAL around the dispersed phase globules, as well as nanoparticles inside the NMAL; oil density $\rho = 804 \text{ kg / m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type: "extra light" oil) [25]; water cut up to 63%; asphaltenes 0.43-1.78% [27](actual concentration of asphaltenes according to the field data is ~0.67%). Forecasts for PNBPCO, expected: weak manifestation of PNBPCO only at the level of the dispersion medium due to asphaltene micellar nanostructure; a decrease in the effectiveness of demulsifiers is not expected, therefore, the tested demulsifiers should generally exhibit the properties of super demulsifiers (SD).

Crude oil from the "Komsomolskoye" LLP field. Required information on the field and forecasts regarding the PNBPCO: the field has been in operation since 1984; the annual volume of oil production is ~62,230 tons; the oil emulsion is not at all stable and refers mainly to a coarsely dispersed system, which is instantly destroyed during thermochemical treatment with the help of demulsifiers; there is a very weak asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase; there are no nanoscale dispersed phase, NMAL around the dispersed phase globules, as well as nanoparticles inside the NMAL; oil density $\rho = 791 \text{ kg / m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type: "extra light" oil) [GOST R 51858-2002];

water cut up to 51%; asphaltenes in gray is ~0.33% [28]. Forecasts for PNBPCO, expected: very weak manifestation of PNBPCO only at the level of the dispersion medium due to asphaltene micellar nanostructure; a decrease in the effectiveness of demulsifiers is not expected, therefore, the tested demulsifiers should generally exhibit the properties of super demulsifiers (SD).

Crude oil from the field of "Emir-oil" LLP. Required information on the field and forecasts regarding the PNBPCO: the field has been in operation since 2002; the annual volume of oil production is ~155,000 tons; the oil emulsion is not at all stable and refers mainly to a coarsely dispersed system, which is instantly destroyed during thermochemical treatment with the help of demulsifiers; there is a very weak asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase; there are no nanoscale dispersed phase, NMAL around the dispersed phase globules, as well as nanoparticles inside the NMAL; oil density $\rho = 789 \text{ kg / m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type: "extra light" oil) [GOST R 51858-2002]; water cut up to 58%; asphaltenes are 0.07-0.71%, and the actual concentration of asphaltenes, according to the deposit data, is ~0.16% [27]. Forecasts for PNBPCO: expected: very weak manifestation of PNBPCO only at the level of the dispersion medium due to asphaltene micellar nanostructure; a decrease in the effectiveness of demulsifiers is not expected, therefore, the tested demulsifiers should generally exhibit the properties of super demulsifiers (SD).

Generalized Forecasts for the Strength of PNBPCO Depending on the Concentration of Asphaltenes and the Density of Crude Oil:

- With an increase in the concentration of asphaltenes ($\geq 3\%$) in crude oil and the density of crude oil ($\geq 830\text{-}840 \text{ kg / m}^3$), a sharp increase in the strength of PNBPCO is expected at all levels of the nanostructure, due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and in as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAS) around the globules of the dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside the NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure, (for example, in cases oil fields "Uzen", "Zhetybai", "Zhalgizobemunai");
- With a decrease in the concentration of asphaltenes in crude oil ($\leq 0.7\%$), as well as the density of crude oil ($\leq 810 \text{ kg / m}^3$), oil emulsions are mainly referred to completely unstable macroemulsions and coarse-dispersed systems, and the absence of PNBPCO and a sharp decrease in the strength of PNBPCO in dispersion environment and instant 100% destruction of such emulsions during thermochemical treatment using tested demulsifiers (for example, in the cases crude oil from "Akkulka", "Komsomolskoye", "Emir-oil" fields).

Samples of Demulsifiers from Some of the World's Leading Companies:

Demulsifiers of the Chinese company PE:

In world practice, block copolymers of alkylene oxides (mainly ethylene and propylene oxides) based on polyhydric alcohols, amines, phenol-formaldehyde resins, epoxy resins, organosilicon compounds, and other compounds are mainly used as surfactant demulsifiers [3, 34]. The most practical demulsifiers are compounds of the type of block copolymers of ethylene and propylene oxides based on polyhydric alcohols [31]. According to the degree of atomicity of alcohols, such copolymers can be classified as follows: two-branched copolymers based on dihydric alcohols, for example, ethylene glycol; three-branched copolymers based on trihydric alcohols such as glycerin; tetra-branched copolymers based on tetrahydric alcohols such as pentaerythritol; five-branched copolymers based on pentahydric alcohols such as xylitol, etc. Block copolymers typically include oxyethylene chain blocks and oxypropylene chain blocks. The demulsifier molecules are mainly composed of three alkylene blocks: two oxypropylene blocks and one oxyethylene block; two oxyethylene block and one oxypropylene block [3, 43]. In the literature, no information has been found about multiblock (more than three) demulsifiers, as well as demulsifiers consisting of one-branched copolymers based on monohydric alcohols. Therefore, demulsifiers consisting of a single-branched copolymer of ethylene and propylene oxides based on n-decyl alcohol (SBCEPOBDA) with various amounts (g) of oxyethylene and oxypropylene blocks (g = 1; 2; 3; 5; 7; 9). The molecular weight of all samples was approximately 4000 ± 12 ; fourteen:

1. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{87}$
2. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{66}$
3. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{23}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{49}\text{H}$
4. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{49}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{23}\text{H}$
5. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{12}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{49}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{11}\text{H}$ (PNS);
6. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{24}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{23}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{25}\text{H}$ (PNS);
7. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_8(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{24}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_8(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{25}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_7\text{H}$ (PNS);
8. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{16}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{12}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{16}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_{11}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{17}\text{H}$ (PNS);
9. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_6(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{16}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_6(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{16}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_6(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{17}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_5\text{H}$ (PNS);
10. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{12}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_8(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{12}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_8(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{12}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_7(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O})_{13}\text{H}$ (PNS);

11. $C_{10}H_{21}O(C_2H_4O)_5(C_3H_6O)_{12}(C_2H_4O)_5(C_3H_6O)_{12}(C_2H_4O)_5(C_3H_6O)_{12}(C_2H_4O)_4(C_3H_6O)_{13}(C_2H_4O)_4H$ (PNS);
 12. $C_{10}H_{21}O(C_3H_6O)_9(C_2H_4O)_6(C_3H_6O)_{10}C_2H_4O_6(C_3H_6O)_{10}(C_2H_4O)_6(C_3H_6O)_{10}(C_2H_4O)_5(C_3H_6O)_{10}H$ (PNS);
- Conditional symbols of the above simple oligomers type the SBCEPOBDA:

1. D4001-25-1-(OE-1-87; OP-0)-50
2. D4001-0-1-(OP-1-66; OE-0)-50
3. D4001-25-2-(OE-1-23; OP-1-49)-50
4. D4001-25-2-(OP-1-49; OE-1-23)-50
5. D4001-25-3-(OE-2: 12, 11; OP-1: 49)-50(PNS);
6. D4001-25-3-(OP-2: 24, 25; OE-1: 23)-50(PNS);
7. D4001-25-5-(OE-3: 8, 8, 7; OP-2: 24, 25)-50(PNS);
8. D4001-25-5-(OP-3: 16, 16, 17; OE-2: 12, 11)-50(PNS);
9. D4001-25-7-(OE-4: 6, 6, 6, 5; OP-3: 16, 16, 17)-50(PNS);
10. D4001-25-7-(OP-4: 12, 12, 12, 13; OE-3: 8, 8, 7)-50(PNS);
11. D4001-25-9-(OE-5: 5, 5, 5, 4, 4; OP-4: 12, 12, 12, 13)-50(PNS);
12. D4001-25-9-(OP-5: 9, 10, 10, 10, 10; OE-4: 6, 6, 6, 5)-50(PNS);

An example of decoding conditional formulas:

D4001-25-3-(OE-2: 12, 11; OP-1: 49)-50

D - demulsifier; 4001 - denotes molecular mass (M), $M = 4012 \approx 4000$; 1 in the number 4001 denotes the atomicity number of alcohols, i.e. in these cases we are talking about ethers of monoatomic n-aliphatic alcohols; 25 - the percentage of oxyethylene ($-C_2H_4O-$); 3 - the total number of blocks chains of ethylene and propylene oxides; OE - oxyethylene chain; 2 - the number of the blocks oxyethylene chain; 12, 11 - the number of oxyethylene groups ($-C_2H_4O-$); 1 - the number of the block oxypropylene chain; 49 - the number of oxypropylene groups ($-C_3H_6O-$); 50 - concentration of the active phase of the considered demulsifiers. A critical nanoemulsions were be used as a solvents [20, 29, 30].

Russian Demulsifiers:

Proxanol-146; Proxanol-186; Proxamine HP-71; Proxamine-385; TND;SNPKh-4315D; Fleck-D020; DE;Nedra-1M; FORE-2E; Reapon-4B.

Demulsifiers of Germany:

(Joint company of Germany and Kazakhstan "Almatyneftekhim", production in Atyrau): Dissolvan-4411; Dissolvan V 5748; Dissolvan15011; Dissolvan-4795; Dissolvan-4397.

Demulsifiers of Kazakhstan:

(Almatyneftekhim, production in Atyrau): IKHLAS-1 (PNS);IKHLAS-3 (PNS);IKHLAS-9 (PNS);IKHLAS-21 (PNS);IKHLAS-26 (PNS);IKHLAS-32 (PNS);IKHLAS-36 (PNS);IKHLAS-37 (PNS) [31].

Demulsifiers USA (DOW Company) [32]:

DEMTROL-2020; DEMTROL-2025; DEMTROL-2030; DEMTROL-3000; DEMTROL-3005; DEMTROL-3010; DEMTROL-3020; DEMTROL-4017; DEMTROL-4026; DEMTROL-4110; DEMTROL-4115; DEMTROL-4120; DEMTROL-5030; DEMTROL-5050; DEMTROL-5130; DEMTROL-5150.

Demulsifiers USA (company "Baker Hughes") [33]:

DMO-080041; DMO-86520; DMO-86334

Demulsifiers USA - Kazakhstan (Rauan Nalco company) [34]:

Randem-2201; Randem-2203; Randem-2208; Randem-2210; Randem-2219; Randem-2224; Randem-2226.

Demulsifiers of the Chinese company E400:

E-401 (Chin com-y 400); E-401 (Chin com-y 400); E-401 (Chin com-y 400); E-401 (Chin com-y 400).

Demulsifiers of the Chinese Company E500:

E-501 ÷ 536 (Chin com-y 500)

Demulsifiers of the Chinese Company E600:

E-602 (Chin com-y 600); E-603 (Chin com-y 600); E-607 (Chin com-y 600); E-610 (Chin com-y 600); E-611 (Chin com-y 600); E-612 (Chin com-y 600).

Research Methods:

The quality of oil in terms of water content (no more than 0.5%), chloride salts (no more than 100 mg / dm^3), mechanical impurities (no more than 0.05%) and the quality of formation water in terms of oil content (no more than 50 mg / dm^3) must meet the requirements of existing standards [35, 36]. The experimental part of the work was carried out according to generally accepted methods for a complete establishment of the effectiveness of demulsifiers (the methods are presented in an abbreviated form):

- *Procedure for determining the demulsifying activity of chemical reagents.* Purpose of the method: The method allows you to determine the effectiveness of the demulsifier in comparison with the base demulsifier and to recommend the most effective demulsifier for experimental-industrial tests . For research can be used field and artificially prepared oil-water emulsions [70]. The disadvantage of the

method is the admissibility of the adequacy of the oil-field and artificially prepared oil-water emulsions. Such adequacy, in our opinion, is erroneous;

- *Method for determination of water in oil products and oil.* The essence of the method: The tested oil products or oil are heated in a flask with a refrigerator (on the Dean-Stark apparatus) in the presence of a water-immiscible solvent, which is distilled together with the water in the sample. Nefras 80/120 (gasoline "galosh") was used as a solvent. The condensed solvent and water are constantly separated in the trap, with the water remaining in the graduated compartment of the trap and the solvent returning to the distillation vessel [37];
- *Method for determining the content of chloride salts in oil.* The essence of the method lies in the extraction of chloride salts from oil with distilled water and their indicator titration in an aqueous extract. The aqueous extract is cooled to room temperature and preparation for titration by indicator is carried out. During indicator titration, 2 cm³ of 0.2 mol/dm³ of nitric acid solution and 10 drops of diphenylcarbazide are poured into a flask with a water extract prepared for titration and is titrated with 0.005 mol/dm³ with a solution of mercury nitrate until a weak pink color, which does not disappear within 1 min. The color of the analyzed solution is compared with distilled water водой [38]. The main disadvantages of the method, in our opinion, are associated with certain subjective reasons of the experimenter;
- *Method for determining the content of mechanical impurities in oil.* The essence of the method consists in filtering the test products with preliminary dissolution of slowly filtering products in gasoline or toluene, washing the precipitate on the filter with a solvent, followed by drying and weighing [39]. The main disadvantage of the method in our opinion is the error associated with the pore size of the filter papers. The smallest pore size (2-3 μm) is filter paper with a green ribbon [39]. Consequently, when determining the content of mechanical impurities in oil, a certain part of mechanical impurities with a particle size of less than 2-3 μm pass through the filter pores during filtration of the solution, as a result is take place of which the error of experiment [39];
- *Method for determination of oil content in water.* The essence of the method: The method is based on the extraction (extraction) of oil from water with an organic solvent (chloroform, etc.), which dissolves oil, but itself practically does not dissolve in water. Nefras 80/120 was used as a solvent. Oil dissolved in solvent stains it. The color intensity is proportional to the oil concentration. In this case, photometers of various brands are used (photoelectric colorimeters, spectrophotometers). We used a PE-5300VI spectrophotometer (manufactured in Russia, St. Petersburg). Method error is less than ± 1% [36].

Revealing the polybarrier properties of crude oil from various fields of the Republic of Kazakhstan using comparative results of laboratory tests (bottle tests) of samples of numerous demulsifiers of some leading companies in the world for breaking oil emulsions was carried out using the data in Table 2.

3. Results and Discussion:

Revealing the nanobarrier properties of crude oil from various fields of the Republic of Kazakhstan implemented using comparative results of laboratory tests (bottle tests) of samples of numerous demulsifiers of the above-mentioned leading companies in the world (Table 2). Revealing the nanobarrier properties of crude oil is the main element of the corresponding scientific discovery with the following formula: Theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed a previously unknown polynanobarrier property of crude oil due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanosized dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the dispersed phase globules, nanoparticles inside the NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure. Consequently, demulsifiers with a polynanostructure, in contrast to demulsifiers without a polynanostructure, very easily overcome the polynanobarrier structure of crude oil. Therefore, before presenting a commentary and interpretations according to the data in the table 2, one should provide the necessary information on the polynanostructure of demulsifiers. Literary search for polynanostructured demulsifiers turned out to be ineffective, because questions on polynanostructured demulsifiers are considered also for the first time. The concept of polynanostructure is also presented as a new property for surfactants (surfactant - demulsifiers and surfactant - desuspensers) and is considered for the first time. By the authors of the scientific discovery, polynanostructural properties are included in the list of requirements for nanodemulsifiers [18, 19, 22, 23]. We will try to reveal the essence of each nanostructure separately (with reference to the publications of the authors of the scientific discovery and other authors), which together are expressed as the polynanostructure of systems:

- Micellar nanostructure of block copolymers of ethylene and propylene oxides based on colloidal surfactants (BSOEPOBOCS, or surfactant demulsifiers), as a nanoheterogeneous system is characterized with a sharp bend in surfactant isotherms surface tension (σ)—concentration (C) and the corresponding concentration is called the critical concentration of micelle formation (CCM), i.e. the

presence of CCM is a clear generally accepted feature of the micellar nanostructure of colloidal systems [11, 12, 40-46];

- Micellar nanostructure of additives of nonionic surfactants such as ethoxylated esters of n-aliphatic alcohols or acids [43, 45] as a wetting agent for nanodemulsifiers-nanodesuspensers of the "IKHLAS" type [29, 30, 31];
- Nano-liquid crystal structure BSOEPOBOCS [22, 47]. In fig. 1 shows the images of some concentrate samples of liquid crystal nanodemulsifier (LCND) "IKHLAS" in glass vials in vertical (3 vials) and horizontal (3 vials) positions. The arrangement of the vials in vertical and horizontal positions is a confirmation of the liquid state of these IKHLAS LCND samples. The images on the inner surfaces of the vials confirm the crystalline state of the IKHLAS LCND samples. Thus, in contrast to those described in the known literature [48], for the first time on the examples of the substances under study, the visual observation of the liquid crystal state for the considered nano-demulsifiers-nanodesuspensers is unambiguously confirmed. It is possible that there are nano-sized crystals [49], in the volume, which are adsorbed on the inner surface of glass bottles, as a result of which multilayers of visually observed crystals are formed. We found similar phenomena for nanoparticles of bentonite clay and iron salts during the destruction of oil emulsions of the "Buzovny" fields of Azerbaijan and "Uzen" of the Republic of Kazakhstan [50]. Indeed, some authors have established that liquid crystals have nanosizes (up to 100 nm) [49, 51, 52].

Figure 1: Images of some concentrate samples of LCND "IKHLAS" in glass bottles in vertical and horizontal positions: 1 - LCND "IKHLAS" 6003-20; 2 - LCND "IKHLAS" 5003-15; 3 - LCND "IKHLAS" 4003-10.

From this point of view, liquid crystal demulsifiers "IKHLAS" also belong to nanostructured liquid crystal systems [21-23]. Along with the traditional aggregate states of matter (gas, liquid, solid) accepted in world terminology, hybrid aggregate states of matter are also possible. From this point of view, liquid crystals can be considered as a hybrid of liquid and solid (crystalline) state of aggregation of matter. On the other hand, it is very important which state of aggregation plays a dominant role in the hybrid variant (the questions are considered for the first time). The liquid state of aggregation plays a dominant role in the IKHLAS liquid-crystalline nano-demulsifiers-nanodesuspensers. Therefore, it is necessary to conventionally note the cases of hybrid units. It can be assumed that the first letter denotes the dominant role in the hybrid. The LC symbol is suitable for IKHLAS liquid-crystalline nano-demulsifier-nanodesuspenser hybrids. It is known that the solid state of a substance can exist in crystalline and amorphous forms. Consequently, in the case of a liquid amorphous hybrid, if the predominance belongs to the liquid, the corresponding sign will be LA. With this approach, the following possible hybrid aggregated cases can be considered: LC; LA; CL; AL; LG; GL; CG; AG; GC; GA (where L – liquid; C – crystal; A – amorph; G – gas). First of all, the problem under consideration is of particular interest as one of the new trends of colloidal chemistry; of modern molecular physics; of petrochemistry; of petrochemical physics; of oilfield nanotechnology and of oil nanotechnology in general,

since there is no information on the hybrid state of aggregation for organic substances. It should be noted that Professor L.P. Semikhina et al. noted that the TND demulsifier (Tyumen nanodemulsifier) and other similar compounds are also liquid crystals [53-57]. However, the results of experimental - industrial tests (2019) of the LPT at the Phystech II field turned out to be insufficiently effective, compared to the basic IKHLAS-1 nanodemulsifier with PNS. A hybrid state of matter from the point of view of a previously unknown property of matter can also be the subject of scientific discovery. For example, physicists from the University of Edinburgh of Scotland (published on the Internet on April 10, 2019) made a statement about a liquid-crystalline hybrid state for inorganic substances, in examples of potassium and sodium under extreme conditions of synthesis (high temperature and high pressure - 20,000 atmosphere pressure) [58]. Thus, the hybrid state of aggregation is a new area both for inorganic substances in the examples of metals in the form of alkali metal atoms, as well as for organic substances, in the examples of nanodemulsifiers - nanodesuspensifiers of the "IKHLAS" type.

• **Nanocluster Structure of Alcohols [11, 59-63]:**

Table 1 shows the literature, experimental and theoretical data for the value of the dynamic viscosity of n-aliphatic alcohols and comparative deviations. Based on the data in Table 1, using the least squares, the following correlations were obtained $\mu = f(m)$ in different intervals of the value of m (the number of carbon atoms in hydrocarbon radicals of n-aliphatic alcohols):

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= -0,25 + 0,75m & m &= 1 - 5 & (1) \\ \mu &= -3,5 + 1,337m & m &= 5 - 8 & (2) \\ \mu &= -879,2 + 110,8m & m &= 8 - 9 & (3) \\ \mu &= -110 + 25m & m &= 9 - 12 & (4) \end{aligned}$$

Correlation expressions (1) ÷ (4) are shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1: Literature, experimental and theoretical data on dynamic viscosity for n-aliphatic alcohols and corresponding deviations of theoretical data

Alcohols	dynamic viscosity (25°C), mPa·s			Deviations of theoretical data, %	
	Literature Data [59]	Experimental data	Theoretical data	According to literature data	According to Experimental data
CH ₃ OH	0,54	0,52	0,50	-7,4	-3,8
C ₂ H ₅ OH	1,1	1,2	1,2	+9,1	0
C ₃ H ₇ OH	1,95	1,98	2,0	+2,5	+1,0
C ₄ H ₉ OH	2,54	2,60	2,7	+6,3	+3,8
C ₅ H ₁₁ OH	3,5	3,6	3,5	0	-2,8
C ₆ H ₁₃ OH	4,5	4,5	4,5	0	0
C ₇ H ₁₅ OH	5,70	5,65	5,8	+1,7	+2,6
C ₈ H ₁₇ OH	7,3	7,3	7,2	-1,3	-1,3
C ₉ H ₁₉ OH	116	118	115	-0,8	-2,5
C ₁₀ H ₂₁ OH	138	137	140	+1,4	+2,2
C ₁₁ H ₂₃ OH	165	163	165	0	+1,2
C ₁₂ H ₂₅ OH	188	191	190	+1,0	-0,5

Figure 2: Isotherms $\mu = f(m)$ for n-aliphatic alcohols: 1 - (m = 1-5); 2 - (m = 5-8); 3 - (m = 8-9); 4 - (m = 9-12)

Before the era of nanotechnology (until the XXI century), individual liquids, including alcohols, were considered homogeneous systems. However, it was later discovered that liquids that are considered homogeneous at the molecular level can have a nanoheterogeneous structure under certain conditions [62, 64]. Of course, since the kinetic state of molecules in liquids is unstable, the concept of the structure of liquids differs from the concept of solids. Thus, the structure of liquids is associated with the formation of associations consisting of several sets of molecules. These associations are called clusters. There are certain similarities and differences between clusters and micelles accordingly of noncolloidal and colloidal surfactants [42, 64, 65]. The main similarity is associated with the nature of molecular associates such as clusters and micelles, since both types of structure belong to nanoheterogeneous systems. Fundamental differences: Unlike clusters, micelle-forming substances consist of colloidal surfactants, ie from micelle-forming surfactants; Unlike clusters for micelle-forming surfactants, there is a concept of critical concentration of micelle formation [42, 43, 45, 64-66]. Since alcohols are noncolloidal surfactants, their nanoheterogeneous structure can only be explained with a nanocluster structure. Indeed, in recent years, some studies of the cluster structure of monoatomic aliphatic alcohols [62] have been carried out. The cluster aggregation number (γ) and the cluster density (ρ_c) play an important role in the structure of alcohols. A sharp increase in either of them or both values of γ and ρ_c can be reflected in sharp changes in the properties of alcohols, especially in viscosity (μ). From this point of view, the data in Table 1 and correlation relations (1) - (4) are of interest. For the first time, based on the correlation $\mu = f(m)$ for n-aliphatic alcohols, the concept of the critical value ($m_c = 9$) of the number of carbon atoms in the aliphatic chain was introduced into colloidal chemistry (as a new property - a potential scientific discovery), which is indirect evidence of the possibility of sharp changes in the cluster structure of alcohols at $m_c \geq 9$. At $m_c = 9$, the viscosity increases sharply (16 times), while the average increase in viscosity with each previous increase in m_c (at $m_c < 9$) by one unit was approximately 1.5 times (Table 1) [63]. It should be noted that the conducted literature surveys did not reveal such information for non-colloidal and colloidal surfactants. For the hydrocarbon radical of a surfactant, there is only the Duclos-Traube rule: The surface activity of the surfactant at the solution-air interface is the higher, the longer the length of the hydrocarbon radical, and on average it increases by 3.2 times for each -CH₂- group. 3.2 is called the Duclos-Traube number (β) [43]. According to our data, $\beta = 4.22$ [45]. The values of γ and m_c in the cluster structure of alcohols require a more detailed study. Similar studies for other noncolloidal surfactants with aliphatic chains (-C_mH_{2m} + 1) are also of interest in the future.

- Critical nanoemulsions as solvents (for BSOEPOBOCS) are also one of the varieties of nanostructures of polynanostructured nanodemulsifiers-nanodesuspensifiers [23, 29, 30, 31, 61, 67].
- Intramolecular surface activity of BSOEPOBOCS due to the multiblock nanostructure. In this regard, the authors have a scientific discovery: a previously unknown property of multiblock surfactants similar in structure to block copolymers of ethylene and propylene oxides has been theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed to have an effective demulsifying effect on oil emulsions due to the complex interaction of block copolymers simultaneously with the hydrophilic and hydrophobic phases of the system, which leads to the necessary energy gain for the destruction of oil emulsions, oil nanocolloids, including HDWOE and HDWOS [69], as well as for inhibition of the formation of HDWOE, HDWOS and VES during the primary preparation of oil (PPO) [69, 71]. The development and implementation of polynanostructured demulsifiers to ensure high efficiency of demulsification and desuspensification during the destruction of the most complex oil emulsions and oil nanocolloids in general, including HDWOE and HDWOS, is one of the topical issues of oilfield nanotechnology based on applied nanocolloidal chemistry [11, 12, 18, 19].

Below are some comments and interpretations based on the data in Table 2

For the "Uzen" field of "Ozenmunaigas" JSC:

- Fourfold nanostructure {nanomicellar structure of asphaltenes in a dispersion medium [11, 12, 18-24]; nano-sized particles (droplets) of the dispersed phase; nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the dispersed phase particles; nanoparticles of organic and inorganic origin inside NMAL} is the most important nanocolloidal-chemical property for crude oil (water-oil emulsions) of the "Uzen" field. Actual density $\rho = 844 \text{ kg / m}^3$. Asphaltenes averaged 3.0%;
- Demulsifiers 5-12 (Chin com-y PE) with PNS and all brands of tested demulsifiers of the IKHLAS brand with PNS shows the properties of super demulsifiers (SD) and highly effective demulsifiers (HED) in terms of efficiency. In seven variants, the efficiency is 100%. Demulsifiers are stable and have a ability of desuspensifier (ADS) [67];
- Russian demulsifiers were found to be weak demulsifiers (WD) and very weak demulsifiers (VWD). A relatively high efficiency (95.6%) is manifested for the TND brand (Tyumen nanodemulsifier). The lowest efficiency (48.7%) was found for FORE-2E. Consequently, the tested Russian demulsifiers do not possess PNS properties. For TND, a mononanostructure of the "micellar nanostructure" type [53-

56] is known, i.e. without PNS. The demulsifiers are stable, with the exception of Nedra-1M, which forms VES with crude oil from the "Uzen" field;

- German demulsifiers of the Dissolvan brand were found to be weak demulsifiers (WD), with the exception of Dissolvan15011 as VWD. Therefore, these demulsifiers are without PNS. Dissolvan-4411 is stable, but has a high level of water solubility (hlws); for Dissolvan V 5748 delamination (delam) is observed; Dissolvan15011 forms VES with crude oil from the "Uzen" field; a curd mass is formed (cmf) during storage of Dissolvan-4795 and Dissolvan-4397; the listed negatives do not meet the requirements for demulsifiers [22, 23];
- All 16 brands of DEMTROL (one of the world's leading manufacturers of demulsifiers - the DOW company, USA), according to the results of the conducted bottle tests, were at the VWD level ($D_d < 80\%$), i.e. without PNS;
- All 3 DMO ("Baker Hughes") brands of the well-known and leading world company "Baker Hughes" turned out to be VWD, which is an experimental confirmation of the absence of PNS for these samples, which were not able to overcome through of polybarrier structure of crude oil from the "Uzen" field;
- The tested 6 brands of Randem demulsifiers made in the USA - Kazakhstan (Rauan Nalco company) were at the VWD level (Randem-2208 and Randem-2219 are turned out to be WD), i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome through of polyanobarrier structure of crude oil from the "Uzen" field;
- The efficiency of 40 samples of the Chinese demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 400 and Chin com-y 500 companies were mainly at the level of VWD, i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome the polyanobarrier structure of the crude oil from the "Uzen" field;
- The efficiency of 6 samples of the Chinese demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 600 companies were at the WD level, i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome the poly-barrier structure of crude oil from the Uzen field;
- For crude oil from the "Uzen" field, a previously unknown polyanobarrier property of crude oil was experimentally confirmed due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the globules of dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure.

For the "Zhetybai" field of Mangistaumunaigaz JSC:

- Fourfold nanostructure {nanomicellar structure of asphaltenes in a dispersion medium [11, 12, 18-24]; nano-sized particles (droplets) of the dispersed phase; nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the dispersed phase particles; nanoparticles of organic and inorganic origin inside NMAL} is the most important nanocolloidal-chemical property for crude oil (water-oil emulsions) of the "Zhetybai" field: actual density $\rho = 847 \text{ kg / m}^3$, asphaltenes on average 3.4%;
- Demulsifiers 5-12 (Chin com-y PE) with PNS and all brands of tested demulsifiers of the IKHLAS brand with PNS show the properties of super demulsifiers (SD) and highly effective demulsifiers (HED) in terms of efficiency. In four variants, the efficiency is 100%. Demulsifiers are stable and have a ability of desuspensifier (ADS) [67];
- Russian demulsifiers were found to be weak (WD) and very weak demulsifiers (VWD). A relatively high efficiency (91.8%) is manifested for the TND brand (Tyumen nanodemulsifier). The lowest efficiency (46.3%) was found for FORE-2E. Consequently, the tested Russian demulsifiers do not possess PNS properties. For TND, a mononanostructure of the "micellar nanostructure" type [53-56] is known, i.e. without PNS. The demulsifiers are stable, with the exception of Nedra-1M, which forms VES with crude oil from the "Zhetybai" field;
- German demulsifiers of the Dissolvan brand were found to be weak (WD), with the exception of Dissolvan15011 as VWD. Therefore, these demulsifiers are without PNS. Dissolvan-4411 is stable, but has a high level of water solubility (hlws); for Dissolvan V 5748 delamination (delam) is observed; Dissolvan15011 forms VES with crude oil from the "Zhetybai" field; a curd mass is formed (cmf) during storage of Dissolvan-4795 and Dissolvan-4397; the listed negatives do not meet the requirements for demulsifiers [22, 23];
- All 16 brands of DEMTROL (one of the world's leading manufacturers of demulsifiers - DOW company, USA), according to the results of the bottle tests carried out, were at the VWD level ($D_d < 80\%$), i.e. without PNS;
- All 3 DMO ("Baker Hughes") brands of the well-known and leading world company "Baker Hughes" turned out to be VWD, which is an experimental confirmation of the absence of PNS for these samples,

which were not able to overcome through of polyanobarrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhetybai” field;

- The tested 6 brands of Randemdemulsifiers made in the USA - Kazakhstan (Rauan Nalco company) were at the VWD level (Randem-2208 turned out to be WD), i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome through of polyanobarrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhetybai” field;
- The efficiency of 40 samples of the demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 400 and Chin com-y 500 companies were mainly at the level of VWD, i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome the polyanobarrier structure of the crude oil from the “Zhetybai” field;
- The efficiency of 6 samples of the demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 600 companies were at the WD level, i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome the poly-barrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhetybai” field;
- Thus, for crude oil from the “Zhetybai” field, a previously unknown polyanobarrier property of crude oil was experimentally confirmed due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the globules dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polyananostructure.

For the "Zhalgiztobemunai" Oil Field SLLC:

- Fourfold nanostructure {nanomicellar structure of asphaltenes in a dispersion medium [11, 12, 18-24]; nano-sized particles (droplets) of the dispersed phase; nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the dispersed phase particles; nanoparticles of organic and inorganic origin inside NMAL} is the most important nanocolloidal-chemical property for crude oil (water-oil emulsions) of the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field: actual density $\rho = 947 \text{ kg / m}^3$; asphaltenes on average 5.25%;
- Demulsifiers 5-12 (Chin com-y PE) with PNS and all brands of tested demulsifiers of the IKHLAS brand with PNS show the properties of super demulsifiers (SD) and, in most cases, highly effective demulsifiers (HED). In three variants, the efficiency is 100%. Demulsifiers are stable and have a ability of desuspensifier (ADS) [67];
- Russian demulsifiers were found to be weak (WD) and very weak demulsifiers (VWD). A relatively high efficiency (88.4%) is manifested for the TND brand (Tyumen nanodemulsifier). The lowest efficiency (45.9%) was found for FORE-2E. Consequently, the tested Russian demulsifiers do not possess PNS properties. For TND, a mononanostructure of the "micellar nanostructure" type [53-56] is known, i.e. without PNS. The demulsifiers are stable, with the exception of Nedra-1M, which forms VES with crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field;
- German demulsifiers of the Dissolvan brand were found to be weak (WD), with the exception of Dissolvan15011 as VWD. Therefore, these demulsifiers are without NPS. Dissolvan-4411 is stable, but has a high level of water solubility (hlws); for Dissolvan V 5748 delamination (delam) is observed; Dissolvan15011 forms VES with crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field; a curd mass is formed (cmf) during storage of Dissolvan-4795 and Dissolvan-4397; the listed negatives do not meet the requirements for demulsifiers [22, 23];
- All 16 brands of DEMTROL (one of the world's leading manufacturers of demulsifiers - DOW company, USA), according to the results of the bottle tests carried out, were at the VWD level ($D_d < 80\%$), i.e. without PNS, therefore they did not have the opportunity to overcome through of polyanobarrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field;
- All 3 DMO ("Baker Hughes") brands of the well-known and leading world company "Baker Hughes" turned out to be VWD, which is an experimental confirmation of the absence of PNS for these samples, which were not able to overcome through of polyanobarrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field;
- The tested 4 brands of Randemdemulsifiers (USA – Kazakhstan, Rauan Nalco company) were at the VWD level and 2 brands (Randem-2201 and Randem-2208) were at the WD level, i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome through of polyanobarrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field;
- The efficiency of 40 samples of the Chinese demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 400 and Chin com-y 500 companies were mainly at the level of VWD, i.e. without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome the polyanobarrier structure of the crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field;
- The efficiency of 40 samples of the Chinese demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 400 and Chin com-y 500 companies were mainly at the level of OSLD, i.e. without oil pumping stations, therefore, they did not

have the opportunity to overcome the nanobarrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field;

- The efficiency of 6 samples of the Chinese demulsifiers of the Chin com-y 600 companies were at the WD and VWD level, ie.without PNS, therefore, they did not have the opportunity to overcome the poly-barrier structure of crude oil from the “Zhetybai” field;
- Thus, for crude oil from the “Zhalgiztobemunai” field, a previously unknown polynanobarrier property of crude oil was experimentally confirmed due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the globules dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure.

For “Akkulka” fields, “TethysAralGaz” LLP, “Komsomolskoye” LLP, “Emir-Oil” LLP:

For all three deposits, all demulsifiers tested were found to be super demulsifiers (SD). Exceptions are the samples of Russian demulsifiers DE and FORE-2E, which are characterized, also emulsifying properties, therefore, during experimental - industrial tests of these reagents at the “Zhetybai” and “Uzen” fields, more serious complications arose in the primary preparation of oil. Therefore, DE and FORE-2E are not relevant as demulsifiers for the studied fields. For all three fields no polynanobarrier property of crude oil.

4. Conclusion:

- In conditions of a relatively high concentration of asphaltenes ($\geq 3\%$) in crude oil, as well as a high density of the crude oil itself ($\geq 830\text{kg} / \text{m}^3$), for example, in the cases of the oil fields “Uzen”, “Zhetybai”, “Zhalgiztobemunai”, polynanobarrier properties of crude oil (PNBPCO) is manifested at all levels of the nanostructure, due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanoscale dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around the globules of the dispersed phase, nanoparticles inside the NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure, i.e. under these conditions, the polynanobarrier property of crude oil is manifested.
- Under conditions of a relatively low concentration of asphaltenes ($\leq 0.7\%$) in crude oil, as well as a relatively low density of the crude oil itself ($\leq 810 \text{ kg} / \text{m}^3$), oil emulsions are mainly unstable macroemulsions and coarse - dispersed systems. For example, in the case of the “Akkulka”, “Komsomolskoye”, and “Emir-oil”oil fields, PNBPCO is not manifested at all levels of the nanostructure, as a result of which an instant 100% destruction of such emulsions occurs during thermochemical treatment using all tested demulsifiers. The exceptions were the samples of Russian demulsifiers DE and FORE-2E, which have the properties also of emulsifiers.
- All forecasts for PNBPCO for all fields have found an experimental confirmation.
- Based on the results of the studies, a previously unknown polynanobarrier property of crude oil was theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed due to the asphaltene micellar nanostructure of the dispersion medium as an external nanophase, and as an internal nanomedium, due to the nanosized dispersed phase, nanomolecular adsorption layers (NMAL) around dispersed phase globules, nanoparticles inside NMAL, which together reduce the effectiveness of demulsifiers when dosed into crude oil, especially demulsifiers without polynanostructure.
- Destruction of direct emulsions to the standard level of oil-in-water concentration (no more than $50 \text{ mg} / \text{m}^3$) according to table 2 is conditioned only by polynanostructured demulsifiers 5÷12 (Chin com-y PE) and IKHLAS [31]brand.

Table 2: Comparative results of laboratory tests of samples of various demulsifiers of some leading companies in the world for the destruction of oil emulsions from various fields of the Republic of Kazakhstan to reveal the nanobarrier properties of crude oil

Demulsifier name	Dem. effic	Sc, g/t	T _d , °C	τ, hours	Dem. stab	Con. of wat, %		DEID		ROCW, mg/dm ³	DEDE RBD, at times
						initial W _i	res-l W _r	D _d , %	EDIERBD, at times		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Crude oil from the “Uzen” field of “Ozenmunaigas” JSC of RK (since1965 in expl; AOP =5,5 mln t;viscosity: at 40° 30-40 mPa·s;ρ=844-874, kg/m ³ ; water cut: up to 98%; paraffins: ~25%; asphalt-resinous components up to 20%, asphaltenes 2.7-3.3%, on average 3.0%;T _{pp} =30-32°C[6, 7];)											
5 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,17	99,6	46	46	17,0
6 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,03	99,9	260	39	20,1
7 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	35	22,4
8 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	27	29,0

9 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	34	23,0
10 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	28	27,9
11 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,08	99,8	97	43	18,2
12 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,03	99,9	260	31	25,2
Proxanol-146(Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,3	84,8	1,07	795	0,98
Proxanol-186 (Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,0	85,4	1,11	750	1,04
ProxamineHP-71(Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,1	85,2	1,10	767	1,02
Proxamine-385 (Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,8	83,7	1	778	1,00
TND (Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	2,1	95,6	3,71	73	10,7
SNPX-4315D (Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	8,8	81,7	0,88	290	2,70
Flek-D020 (Rus)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	8,2	82,9	0,95	271	2,89
DE(Rus)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,5	69,8	0,54	797	0,98
NEDRA-1M(Rus)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	13,9	71,0	0,56	790	0,99
FORE-2E (Rus)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	24,6	48,7	0,32	865	0,90
Reapon-4B(Rus)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	11,7	75,6	0,67	548	1,43
Dissolvan-4411 (Germ)	WD	100	62	3	hlws	48	8,0	83,3	0,97	792	0,99
Dissolvan V 5748 (Germ)	WD	100	62	3	delam	48	7,6	84,2	1,02	789	0,99
Dissolvan15011 (Germ)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	11,3	76,4	0,69	694	1,13
Dissolvan-4795 (Germ)	WD	100	62	3	cmf	48	9,0	81,2	0,87	630	1,2 4
Dissolvan-4397 (Germ)	WD	100	62	3	cmf	48	9,6	80,0	0,81	810	0,97
IKHLAS-1PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	18	43,5
IKHLAS-3 PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	35	22,4
IKHLAS-9 PNS	HED	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,15	99,7	52,0	31	25,2
IKHLAS-21PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,12	99,8	65,0	24	32,6
IKHLAS-26PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0	100	∞	19	41,2
IKHLAS-32PNS	SD	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,12	99,8	65,0	22	35,6
IKHLAS-36PNS	HED	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,15	99,7	52,0	23	34,0
IKHLAS-37PNS	HED	100	62	3	St DA	48	0,13	99,7	60,0	21	37,3
DEMTROL-2020(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.1	56.0	0.37	882	0.88
DEMTROL-2025(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.6	55.0	0.36	880	0.89
DEMTROL-2030(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	24.4	49.2	0.32	889	0.88
DEMTROL-3000(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13.8	71.2	0.56	834	0.94
DEMTROL-3005(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12.0	75.0	0.65	829	0.94
DEMTROL-3010(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14.1	70.6	0.55	844	0.93
DEMTROL-3020(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	15.5	67.7	0.50	856	0.91
DEMTROL-4017(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.7	54.8	0.36	877	0.89
DEMTROL-4026(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.8	54.5	0.36	865	0.90
DEMTROL-4110(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.7	54.8	0.36	861	0.91
DEMTROL-4115(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.6	55.0	0.36	873	0.89
DEMTROL-4120(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	21.7	54.8	0.36	858	0.91
DEMTROL-5030(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	26.5	44.7	0.29	894	0.88
DEMTROL-5050(USA)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	18.2	62.1	0.43	835	0.94
DEMTROL-5130(USA))	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	18.3	61.8	0.43	841	0.93
DEMTROL-	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	19.5	59.4	0.40	846	0.92

5150(USA)												
DMO-080041 (USA, BH)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,0	75,0	0.65	560	1.40	
DMO-86520 (USA, BH)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,4	74,2	0.63	527	1.48	
DMO-86334 (USA, BH)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	10,9	77,3	0.72	514	1.52	
Randem-2203 (USA RN)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	12,7	73,5	0.61	894	0.88	
Randem-2208 (USA RN)	WD	100	62	3	ves	48	7,0	85,4	1.11	529	1.48	
Randem-2210 (USA RN)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	11,6	75,8	0.67	621	1.26	
Randem-2219 (USA RN)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	9,5	80,2	0.82	789	0.99	
Randem-2224 (USA RN)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	12,2	74,5	0.64	820	0.95	
Randem-2226 (USA RN)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	10,1	78,9	0.77	803	0.98	
E-401(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	9,8	79,6	0.79	850	0.92	
E-402(Chin com-y 400)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	9,5	80,2	0.82	843	0.93	
E-403(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	10,1	78,9	0.77	861	0.91	
E-404(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	11,8	75,4	0.66	879	0.89	
E-501(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,0	70,8	0.56	916	0.85	
E-502(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	15,1	68,5	0.51	925	0.84	
E-503(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,9	68,9	0.52	914	0.86	
E-504(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	15,8	67,0	0.49	902	0.87	
E-505(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	17,1	64,3	0.46	957	0.82	
E-506(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,6	69,6	0.53	926	0.84	
E-507(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,9	69,0	0.52	930	0.84	
E-508(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	15,2	68,3	0.51	944	0.83	
E-509(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,7	69,4	0.53	913	0.86	
E-510(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	15,5	67,7	0.50	925	0.85	
E-511(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,8	73,3	0.61	872	0.90	
E-512(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,1	72,7	0.59	889	0.88	
E-513(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,4	70,0	0.54	890	0.88	
E-514(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,0	72,9	0.60	874	0.89	
E-515(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	11,9	75,2	0.65	841	0.93	
E-516(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,3	74,3	0.63	868	0.90	
E-517(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,6	71,7	0.57	877	0.89	
E-518(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,7	73,5	0.61	820	0.95	
E-519(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,0	72,9	0.60	816	0.96	
E-520(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	19,5	59,4	0.40	981	0.80	
E-521(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	21,4	55,4	0.36	990	0.79	
E-522(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	ves	48	19,1	60,2	0.41	972	0.80	
E-523(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,1	74,7	0.64	753	1.04	

E-524(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,6	71,6	0.57	762	1.03
E-525(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,5	71,9	0.58	785	0.99
E-526(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	11,4	76,2	0.68	704	1.11
E-527(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,0	75,0	0.65	736	1.06
E-528(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,3	70,2	0.54	785	0.99
E-529(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,1	74,7	0.64	768	1.02
E-530(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	11,1	76,8	0.70	732	1.07
E-531(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	14,6	69,5	0.53	790	0.99
E-532(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	10,9	77,3	0.71	649	1.21
E-533(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	13,7	71,4	0.57	695	1.12
E-534(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	12,1	74,7	0.64	622	1.26
E-535(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	20,6	57,1	0.50	971	0.81
E-536(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	62	3	Stable	48	10,4	78,3	0.75	547	1.43
E-602(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	5,0	89,6	1.56	371	2.11
E-603(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,1	85,2	1.09	596	1.31
E-607(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	6,8	85,8	1.15	508	1.54
E-610(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,8	83,7	1	781	1
E-611(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,9	83,5	0.99	798	0.98
E-612(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	62	3	Stable	48	7,5	84,4	1.04	770	1
Control	-	-	62	3	-	48	34,0	29,2	0,23	828	0,95
Random-2201 (BD)	WD	100	62	3	ves	48	7.8(BD)	83,7	-	783(BD)	-
Crude oil from the "Zhetybai" field of "Mangistaumunaigas" JSC of RK (since 1967 in expl; AOP = 1,1 mln t; viscosity: at 40° 30-40 mPa·s; ρ = 830-870, kg/m ³ ; water cut: up to 97.9%; paraffins: ~25-28%; asphalt -resinous components up to 18/4%, asphaltenes 2.7-3.3%, on average 3.0%; T_{pp} = 30-32°C/B, 9/):											
Demulsifier name	Dem. effic	Sc, g/t	T_d , °C	τ , hours	Dem. stab	Con. of wat, %		DEID		ROCW, mg/dm ³	DEDE RBD, at times
						initial W_i	res-l W_r	D_d , %	EDIERBD, at times		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
5 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,12	99,7	124	47	14,5
6 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,07	99,8	213	42	16,2
7 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0	100	∞	43	15,8
8 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0	100	∞	31	21,9
9 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,09	99,8	165	32	21,3
10 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,03	99,9	496	29	23,4
11 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,15	99,7	99	49	13,9
12 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,09	99,8	165	34	20,0
Proxanol-146(Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12,3	72,6	1,21	635	1,07
Proxanol-186 (Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12,1	73,1	1,23	576	1,18
ProxamineHP-71(Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12,2	72,9	1,22	602	1,13
Proxamine-385 (Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12,9	71,3	1,15	647	1,05

TND (Rus)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	3,7	91.8	2,60	81	8,4
SNPX-4315D (Rus)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	8.9	80,1	1.67	369	1.84
Flek-D020 (Rus)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	8.1	82,0	1.84	354	1.92
DE(Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.6	69,9	1.09	791	0.86
NEDRA-1M(Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	13.2	70,6	1.13	830	0.82
FORE-2E (Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	24.1	46,3	0.62	903	0.75
Reapon-4B(Rus)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12.2	72,8	1.22	472	1.44
Dissolvan-4411 (Germ)	VWD	100	64	3	hlws	45	14.8	67,1	1.00	723	0,94
Dissolvan V 5748 (Germ)	WD	100	64	3	delam	45	7.2	84,0	2.07	707	0,96
Dissolvan15011 (Germ)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	10.5	76.5	1.42	564	1.20
Dissolvan-4795 (Germ)	WD	100	64	3	cmf	45	7.5	83.3	2	585	1.16
Dissolvan-4397 (Germ)	VWD	100	64	3	cmf	45	9.6	78.7	1.55	764	0.89
IKHLAS-1PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0	100	∞	23	29,5
IKHLAS-3 PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,06	99,9	248	38	17,9
IKHLAS-9 PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,17	99,6	87	35	19,4
IKHLAS-21PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,15	99,7	99	27	25,2
IKHLAS-26PNS	SD	100	64	3	St DA	45	0	100	∞	24	28,3
IKHLAS-32PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,14	99,7	106	26	26,1
IKHLAS-36PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,18	99,6	82	28	24,3
IKHLAS-37PNS	HED	100	64	3	St DA	45	0,15	99,7	99	25	27,2
DEMTROL-2020(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	22.8	49.3	0.65	705	0.96
DEMTROL-2025(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	23.1	48.7	0.64	716	0.95
DEMTROL-2030(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	26.0	42.2	0.57	903	0.75
DEMTROL-3000(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.9	66.8	1.00	677	1
DEMTROL-3005(USA))	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.4	68.0	1.03	672	1
DEMTROL-3010(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	15.4	65.7	0.96	695	0.98
DEMTROL-3020(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	16.9	62.4	0.88	694	0.98
DEMTROL-4017(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	23.6	47.5	0.63	718	0.95
DEMTROL-4026(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	23.5	47.8	0.63	725	0.94
DEMTROL-4110(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	22.4	50.2	0.64	709	0.96
DEMTROL-4115(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	23.4	48.0	0.64	726	0.93
DEMTROL-4120(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	23.7	47.3	0.64	730	0.93
DEMTROL-5030(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	28.1	37.5	0.53	924	0.74
DEMTROL-5050(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	19.8	56.0	0.75	801	0.85
DEMTROL-5130(USA))	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	19.9	55.7	0.75	796	0.85
DEMTROL-5150(USA)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	21.0	53.3	0.71	819	0.83
DMO-080041 (USA, BH)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12.1	73.1	1.23	591	1.15
DMO-86520 (USA, BH)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.7	74.0	1.27	576	1.18
DMO-86334 (USA, BH)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	10.9	75.8	1.36	589	1.15
Randem-2203 (USA RN)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	13.2	70.5	1.13	783	0.86
Randem-2208 (USA RN)	WD	100	64	3	ves	45	6.7	85.2	2.22	427	1.59
Randem-2210 (USA RN)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	12.3	72.7	1.21	462	1.47
Randem-2201 (USA RN)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	10.2	77.4	1.46	601	1.13
Randem-2224	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	12.6	71.9	1.18	684	0.99

(USA RN)												
Random-2226 (USA RN)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	9.9	78.0	1.50	670	1.01	
E-401(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.6	74.3	1.28	692	0.98	
E-402(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	9.2	79.6	1.62	621	1.09	
E-403(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	9.5	78.8	1.57	614	1.11	
E-404(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12.4	72.5	1.20	649	1.05	
E-501(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.5	70.0	1.10	668	1.02	
E-502(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	15.0	66.7	0.99	750	0.91	
E-503(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.9	66.9	1	674	1.01	
E-504(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	15.7	65.2	0.95	693	0.98	
E-505(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	16.1	64.1	0.92	726	0.94	
E-506(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.6	67.5	1.02	672	1.01	
E-507(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.2	68.4	1.05	647	1.05	
E-508(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	15.7	65.0	0.95	679	1.00	
E-509(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.2	68.3	1.05	640	1.06	
E-510(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.9	66.8	1	681	0.99	
E-511(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.4	70.1	1.11	704	0.96	
E-512(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.7	69.6	1.09	715	0.95	
E-513(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.6	67.6	1.02	683	0.99	
E-514(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.0	71.2	1.14	617	1.10	
E-515(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.2	75.0	1.33	573	1.18	
E-516(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12.7	71.8	1.17	584	1.16	
E-517(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.8	69.3	1.08	590	1.15	
E-518(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.6	69.8	1.09	641	1.06	
E-519(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.5	70.0	1.10	636	1.07	
E-520(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	19.8	56.0	0.75	862	0.79	
E-521(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	20.3	54.8	0.73	897	0.76	
E-522(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	ves	45	18.7	58.4	0.80	844	0.80	
E-523(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.2	70.7	1.13	670	1.01	
E-524(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.1	68.6	1.05	685	0.99	
E-525(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.0	68.9	1.06	652	1.04	
E-526(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12.1	73.0	1.23	623	1.09	
E-527(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	12.8	71.5	1.16	610	1.11	
E-528(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.9	66.9	1	699	0.97	
E-529(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.0	71.2	1.15	651	1.04	
E-530(Chin com-y 500)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.7	74.0	1.27	564	1.20	
E-531(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.0	68.9	1.06	677	1.00	

E-532(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.4	74.7	1.31	590	1.15
E-533(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	13.7	69.5	1.09	617	1.10
E-534(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.6	74.2	1.28	605	1.12
E-535(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	25.7	42.8	0.58	994	0.68
E-536(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	11.2	75.1	1.33	613	1.11
E-602(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	5.4	88.0	2.76	179	3.80
E-603(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	7.9	82.4	1.89	231	2.94
E-607(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	7.3	83.7	2.04	226	3.00
E-610(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	8.5	81.0	1.75	336	2.02
E-611(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	7.4	83.5	2.01	220	3.09
E-612(Chin com-y 600)	WD	100	64	3	Stable	45	8.3	81.6	1.79	328	2.07
Control	-	-	64	3	-	45	31.2	30.7	0.48	875	0.77
Random-2219 (BD)	VWD	100	64	3	Stable	45	14.9(BD)	66.9	-	680(BD)	-
Crude oil from the Subsidiary LLP "Zhalgiztobemunai" field of RK (since 2003 in expl; AOP=182 000t; $\rho=940 \text{ kg/m}^3$; water cut: up to 32%; paraffins: ~1,8%; resin up to 15%; asphaltenes on average 5.25%; $T_{pp}=30-32^\circ\text{C}/26 \text{ t}$)											
Demulsifier name	Dem. effic	Sc, g/t	$T_{\text{d}}, ^\circ\text{C}$	τ , hours	Dem. stab	Con. of wat, %		DEID		ROCW, mg/dm^3	DEDE RBD, at times
						initial W_i	res-l W_r	$D_{\text{d}}, \%$	EDIERBD, at times		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
5 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.18	99.4	25	50	17.9
6 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.12	99.6	37.5	42	21.3
7 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.09	99.7	50	37	24.2
8 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	400	80	10	St DA	32	0	100	∞	27	33.1
9 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.09	99.7	50	39	22.9
10 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	400	80	10	St DA	32	0	100	∞	27	33.1
11 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	ED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.45	98.6	10	46	19.4
12 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.21	99.3	21.4	33	27.0
Proxanol-146(Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	8.9	72.2	0.50	907	0.98
Proxanol-186 (Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.3	70.9	0.48	915	0.97
ProxamineHP-71(Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.8	69.3	0.46	934	0.96
Proxamine-385 (Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.3	70.9	0.48	917	0.97
TND (Rus)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	3.7	88.4	1.21	97	9.2
SNPX-4315D (Rus)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	5.4	83.1	0.83	911	0.98
Flek-D020 (Rus)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	4.9	84.7	0.92	599	1.49
DE(Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	13.8	56.8	0.33	1203	0.74
NEDRA-1M(Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	9.8	69.3	0.46	1170	0.76
FORE-2E (Rus)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	17.3	45.9	0.26	1377	0.65
Reapon-4B(Rus)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	6.3	80.3	0.71	932	0.96
Dissolvan-4411 (Germ)	VWD	400	80	10	hlws	32	11.2	65.0	0.40	1184	0.75
Dissolvan V 5748 (Germ)	WD	400	80	10	delam	32	6.2	80.6	1.73	925	0.96
Dissolvan15011 (Germ)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	8.0	75.0	0.56	1244	0.72
Dissolvan-4795 (Germ)	WD	400	80	10	cmf	32	5.9	81.6	0.76	950	0.94
Dissolvan-4397 (Germ)	VWD	400	80	10	cmf	32	7.2	77.5	0.63	1208	0.74

IKHLAS-1PNS	SD	400	80	10	St DA	32	0	100	∞	18	49.6
IKHLAS-3 PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.09	99.7	50	38	23.5
IKHLAS-9 PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.21	99.3	21.4	34	26.3
IKHLAS-21PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.27	99.1	16.7	24	37.2
IKHLAS-26PNS	SD	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.03	99.9	150	21	42.5
IKHLAS-32PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.24	99.2	18.7	25	35.7
IKHLAS-36PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.30	99.0	15	25	35.7
IKHLAS-37PNS	HED	400	80	10	St DA	32	0.25	99.2	18	22	40.6
DEMTROL-2020(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	16.4	48.8	0.27	1405	0.64
DEMTROL-2025(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	17.6	45.0	0.25	1436	0.62
DEMTROL-2030(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	19.1	40.3	0.23	1490	0.60
DEMTROL-3000(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.6	63.7	0.39	1194	0.75
DEMTROL-3005(USA))	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.5	67.2	0.43	1102	0.81
DEMTROL-3010(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.6	63.7	0.39	1145	0.78
DEMTROL-3020(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	12.2	61.9	0.37	1167	0.77
DEMTROL-4017(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	17.3	45.9	0.26	1494	0.60
DEMTROL-4026(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	17.5	45.2	0.26	1503	0.59
DEMTROL-4110(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	17.4	45.6	0.26	1522	0.58
DEMTROL-4115(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	16.9	47.2	0.27	1510	0.59
DEMTROL-4120(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	17.3	45.9	0.26	1548	0.57
DEMTROL-5030(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	20.0	37.5	0.23	1583	0.56
DEMTROL-5050(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	15.1	52.8	0.30	1489	0.60
DEMTROL-5130(USA))	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	15.4	51.8	0.29	1462	0.61
DEMTROL-5150(USA)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	15.9	50.4	0.28	1470	0.61
DMO-080041 (USA, BH)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.4	70.6	0.47	1084	0.82
DMO-86520 (USA, BH)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.3	70.9	0.48	1066	0.84
DMO-86334 (USA, BH)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.0	71.9	0.50	1106	0.81
Randem-2203 (USA, RN)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	10.5	67.2	0.43	1123	0.80
Randem-2208 (USA, RN)	WD	400	80	10	ves	32	5.6	82.5	0.80	902	0.99
Randem-2210 (USA, RN)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	9.5	70.3	0.47	1164	0.77
Randem-2219 (USA, RN)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	7.4	76.9	0.61	1112	0.80
Randem-2224 (USA, RN)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	9.2	71.2	0.49	1120	0.80
Randem-2226 (USA RN)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	7.8	75.6	0.58	1100	0.81
E-401(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.2	71.3	0.49	1113	0.80
E-402(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	7.5	76.6	0.60	1097	0.81
E-403(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	7.9	75.3	0.57	1082	0.83
E-404(Chin com-y 400)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.6	70.0	0.47	1134	0.79
E-501(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.3	67.8	0.44	1179	0.76
E-502(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.4	64.3	0.39	1188	0.75
E-503(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.0	65.6	0.41	1200	0.74
E-504(Chin com-y	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.7	63.4	0.38	1231	073

500)												
E-505(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	12.0	62.5	0.37	1287	0.69	
E-506(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.1	65.3	0.40	1272	0.70	
E-507(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.8	66.2	0.42	1255	0.71	
E-508(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.9	62.8	0.38	1224	0.73	
E-509(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.0	65.6	0.41	1236	0.72	
E-510(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.4	64.3	0.39	1244	0.72	
E-511(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.1	68.4	0.44	1211	0.74	
E-512(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.0	68.7	0.45	1206	0.74	
E-513(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.7	66.6	0.42	1198	0.75	
E-514(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.9	69.0	0.45	1165	0.77	
E-515(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	8.6	73.1	0.52	1139	0.78	
E-516(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.0	68.7	0.45	1209	0.74	
E-517(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.5	67.2	0.43	1223	0.73	
E-518(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.8	66.2	0.42	1241	0.72	
E-519(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.1	68.4	0.44	1250	0.71	
E-520(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	14.2	55.6	0.32	1392	0.64	
E-521(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	15.4	51.9	0.29	1469	0.61	
E-522(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	ves	32	14.0	56.2	0.32	1456	0.61	
E-523(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.7	69.7	0.46	1142	0.78	
E-524(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.2	68.1	0.44	1217	0.73	
E-525(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.6	66.9	0.42	1233	0.72	
E-526(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.6	70.0	0.47	1144	0.78	
E-527(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.6	70.0	0.47	1122	0.80	
E-528(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.3	64.7	0.40	1281	0.70	
E-529(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.8	69.3	0.46	1179	0.76	
E-530(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.1	71.6	0.49	1156	0.77	
E-531(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	11.1	65.3	0.40	1260	0.71	
E-532(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	8.3	74.0	0.54	1202	0.74	
E-533(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	10.4	67.5	0.43	1385	0.64	
E-534(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	9.2	71.2	0.49	1348	0.66	
E-535(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	18.5	42.2	0.24	1533	0.58	
E-536(Chin com-y 500)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	8.0	75.0	0.56	1219	0.73	
E-602(Chin com-y 600)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	4.3	86.5	1.05	851	1.05	
E-603(Chin com-y 600)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	6.1	80.9	0.74	940	0.95	
E-607(Chin com-y 600)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	6.0	81.2	0.75	964	0.92	
E-610(Chin com-y 600)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	6.8	78.7	0.66	993	0.90	

E-611(Chin com-y 600)	WD	400	80	10	Stable	32	6.1	80.9	0.74	946	0.94
E-612(Chin com-y 600)	VWD	400	80	10	Stable	32	6.6	79.3	0.68	967	0.92
Control	-	-	80	10	-	32	28	12.5	0,16	1134	0,77
Random-2208 (BD)	WD	400	80	10	ves	32	4.5 (BD)	85.9	-	894(BD)	-
Crude oil from the "Akkulka" field "TethysAralGas" LLP of RK (since 2011 in expl; AOP = 255000 τ; ρ = 804 kg/m ³ , water cut: 63%; asphaltene on average ~0.67% [27])											
Demulsifier name	Dem. effic	Sc, g/t	T _d , °C	τ, hours	Dem. stab	Con. of wat, %		DEID		ROCW ₃ mg/dm ³	DEDE RBD, at times
						initial W _i	res-l W _r	D _d , %	EDIERBD, at times		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
5 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	39	3.5
6 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	34	4.0
7 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	32	4.3
8 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	23	5.9
9 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	36	3.8
10 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	33	4.1
11 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	41	3.3
12 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	38	3.6
Proxanol-146(Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	144	0.95
Proxanol-186 (Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	135	1.01
ProxamineHP-71(Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	140	0.98
Proxamine-385 (Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	158	0.87
TND (Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	107	1.28
SNPX-4315D (Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	129	1.06
Flek-D020 (Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	122	1.12
DE (Rus)	WD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	3.9	93.8	-	193	0.71
NEDRA-1M(Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	141	0.97
FORE-2E (Rus)	WD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	4.7	92.5	-	184	0.74
Reapon-4B(Rus)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	130	1.05
Dissolvan-4411 (Germ)	SD	42	47	0.15	hlws	63	0	100	-	157	0.87
Dissolvan V 5748 (Germ)	SD	42	47	0.15	delam	63	0	100	-	145	0.94
Dissolvan15011(Germ)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	152	0.90
Dissolvan-4795 (Germ)	SD	42	47	0.15	cmf	63	0	100	-	129	1.06
Dissolvan-4397 (Germ)	SD	42	47	0.15	cmf	63	0	100	-	144	0.95
IKHLAS-1PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	17	8.0
IKHLAS-3 PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	22	6.2
IKHLAS-9 PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	24	5.7
IKHLAS-21PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	31	4.4
IKHLAS-26PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	23	5.9
IKHLAS-32PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	25	5.5
IKHLAS-36PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	28	4.9
IKHLAS-37PNS	SD	42	47	0.15	St DA	63	0	100	-	27	5.1
DEMTROL-2020(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	144	0.95
DEMTROL-2025(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	156	0.88
DEMTROL-2030(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	159	0.86
DEMTROL-3000(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	142	0.96
DEMTROL-3005(USA))	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	139	0.98

DEMTROL-3010(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	147	0.93
DEMTROL-3020(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	154	0.89
DEMTROL-4017(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	168	0.81
DEMTROL-4026(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	179	0.76
DEMTROL-4110(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	170	0.80
DEMTROL-4115(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	165	0.83
DEMTROL-4120(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	181	0.76
DEMTROL-5030(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	188	0.73
DEMTROL-5050(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	147	0.93
DEMTROL-5130(USA))	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	150	0.91
DEMTROL-5150(USA)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	153	0.90
DMO-080041 (USA, BH)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	130	1.05
DMO-86334 (USA, BH)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	121	1.13
Randem-2203 (USA RN)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	184	0.74
Randem-2208 (USA RN)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	133	1.03
Randem-2210 (USA RN)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	138	0.99
Randem-2219 (USA RN)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	167	0.82
Randem2224 (USA RN)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	168	0.81
Randem-2226 (USA RN)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	155	0.88
E-401(Chin com-y 400)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	152	0.90
E-402(Chin com-y 400)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	146	0.94
E-403(Chin com-y 400)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	141	0.97
E-404(Chin com-y 400)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	160	0.85
E-501(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	148	0.92
E-502(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	154	0.89
E-503(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	152	0.90
E-504(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	170	0.80
E-505(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	163	0.84
E-506(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	154	0.89
E-507(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	146	0.94
E-508(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	139	0.98
E-509(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	151	0.91
E-510(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	158	0.87
E-511(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	142	0.96
E-512(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	143	0.96
E-513(Chin com-y 500))	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	160	0.85
E-514(Chin com-y	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	165	0.83

500)											
E-515(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	165	0.83
E-516(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	149	0.92
E-517(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	151	0.91
E-518(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	170	0.80
E-519(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	168	0.81
E-520(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	185	0.74
E-521(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	191	0.72
E-522(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	182	0.75
E-523(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	180	0.76
E-524(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	173	0.79
E-525(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	189	0.72
E-526(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	154	0.89
E-527(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	147	0.93
E-528(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	162	0.84
E-529(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	186	0.73
E-530(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	145	0.94
E-531(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	159	0.86
E-532(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	154	0.89
E-533(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	170	0.80
E-534(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	167	0.82
E-535(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	190	0.72
E-536(Chin com-y 500)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	141	0.97
E-602(Chin com-y 600)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	139	0.98
E-603(Chin com-y 600)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	146	0.94
E-607(Chin com-y 600)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	150	0.91
E-610(Chin com-y 600)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	144	0.95
E-611(Chin com-y 600)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	155	0.88
E-612(Chin com-y 600)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	141	0.97
Control	-	-	47	0.15	-	63	6.9	89	-	172	0.80
“DMO-86520” (BD)	SD	42	47	0.15	Stable	63	0	100	-	137(BD)	-
Crude oil from the “Komsomolskoye” LLP field of RK (since 1984 in expl; AOP =62230 τ; ρ=791 kg/m ³ ; water cut: 51%; asphaltenes on average ~0,33% [28])											
Demulsifier name	Dem. effic	Sc, g/t	T _d , °C	τ, hours	Dem. stab	Con. of wat, %		DEID		ROCW, mg/dm ³	DEDE RBD, at times
						initial W _i	res-l W _r	D _d , %	EDIERBD, at times		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
5 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	36	2.5
6 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	33	2.8
7 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	27	3.4
8 (Chin com-y	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	20	4.6

PE)PNS											
9 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	34	2.7
10 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	24	3.8
11 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	37	2.5
12 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	33	2.8
Proxanol-146(Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	85	1.08
Proxanol-186 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	99	0.93
ProxamineHP-71(Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	113	0.81
Proxamine-385 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	104	0.88
TND (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	68	1.3
SNPX-4315D (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	110	0.84
Flek-D020 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	105	0.87
DE(Rus)	WD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	2,4	95.3	-	158	0.58
NEDRA-1M(Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	160	0.57
FORE-2E (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	3,5	93.1	-	163	0.56
Reapon-4B(Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	115	0.80
Dissolvan-4411 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	hlws	51	0	100	-	136	0.67
Dissolvan V 5748 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	delam	51	0	100	-	101	0.91
Dissolvan15011(Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	120	0.77
Dissolvan-4795 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	cmf	51	0	100	-	117	0.78
Dissolvan-4397 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	cmf	51	0	100	-	134	0.69
IKHLAS-1PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	16	5.7
IKHLAS-3 PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	21	4.4
IKHLAS-9 PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	21	4.4
IKHLAS-21PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	28	3.3
IKHLAS-26PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	19	4.8
IKHLAS-32PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	20	4.6
IKHLAS-36PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	25	3.7
IKHLAS-37PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	51	0	100	-	24	3.8
DEMTROL-2020(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	103	0.89
DEMTROL-2025(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	114	0.81
DEMTROL-2030(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	118	0.78
DEMTROL-3000(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	99	0.93
DEMTROL-3005(USA))	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	109	0.84
DEMTROL-3010(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	113	0.81
DEMTROL-3020(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	106	0.87
DEMTROL-4017(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	125	0.74
DEMTROL-4026(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	122	0.75
DEMTROL-4110(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	116	0.79
DEMTROL-4115(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	110	0.84
DEMTROL-4120(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	131	0.70
DEMTROL-5030(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	136	0.67
DEMTROL-5050(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	105	0.88
DEMTROL-5130(USA))	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	105	0.88

DEMTROL-5150(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	98	0.94
DMO-080041 (USA, BH)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	90	1.02
DMO-86334 (USA, BH)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	92	1.00
Randem-2203 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	129	0.71
Randem-2208 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	95	0.97
Randem-2210 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	98	0.94
Randem-2219 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	133	0.69
Randem-2224 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	130	0.71
Randem-2226 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	124	0.74
E-401(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	127	0.72
E-402(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	122	0.75
E-403(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	128	0.72
E-404(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	105	0.88
E-501(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	139	0.66
E-502(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	123	0.75
E-503(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	144	0.64
E-504(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	140	0.66
E-505(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	131	0.70
E-506(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	134	0.67
E-507(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	126	0.73
E-508(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	130	0.71
E-509(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	124	0.74
E-510(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	119	0.77
E-511(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	123	0.75
E-512(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	126	0.73
E-513(Chin com-y 500))	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	127	0.72
E-514(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	132	0.69
E-515(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	128	0.72
E-516(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	135	0.68
E-517(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	135	0.68
E-518(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	129	0.71
E-519(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	136	0.68
E-520(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	132	0.70
E-521(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	117	0.77
E-522(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	122	0.82
E-523(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	97	0.95
E-524(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	104	0.88

500)											
E-525(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	112	0.82
E-526(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	116	0.79
E-527(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	129	0.71
E-528(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	138	0.66
E-529(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	120	0.77
E-530(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	119	0.77
E-531(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	107	0.86
E-532(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	125	0.74
E-533(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	131	0.70
E-534(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	123	0.75
E-535(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	149	0.62
E-536(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	130	0.71
E-602(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	98	0.94
E-603(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	135	0.68
E-607(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	97	0.95
E-610(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	108	0.85
E-611(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	104	0.88
E-612(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	116	0.79
Control	-	-	47	0,15	-	51	5.2	89.8	-	140	0.66
«ДМО 86520» (BD)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	51	0	100	-	92 (BD)	-
Crude oil from the LLP "Emir-oil" field of RK (since 2002 in expl; AOP = 155 000 т; $\rho = 789 \text{ kg/m}^3$; water cut: 58%; asphaltenes on average ~0,16% [27])											
Demulsifier name	Demeffic	Sc, g/t	$T_d, ^\circ\text{C}$	τ , hours	Dem. stab	Con. of wat, %		DEID		ROCW ₃ , mg/dm ³	DEDE RBD, at times
						initial W_i	res-l W_r	D_d , %	EDIERBD, at times		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
5 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	33	2.2
6 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	30	2.5
7 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	29	2.6
8 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	19	3
9 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	30	2.5
10 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	25	2.7
11 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	37	2
12 (Chin com-y PE)PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	35	2.1
Proxanol-146 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	69	1.07
Proxanol-186 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	75	0.98
ProxamineHP-71 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	84	0.88
Proxamine-385 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	73	1.01
TND (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	57	1.30
SNPX-4315D (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	60	1.23

Flek-D020 (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	66	1.12
DE(Rus)	WD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	2.1	96.3	-	98	0.75
NEDRA-1M(Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	91	0.81
FORE-2E (Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	2.9	95.0	-	115	0.64
Reapon-4B(Rus)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	71	1.04
Dissolvan-4411 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	hlws	58	0	100	-	88	0.84
Dissolvan V 5748 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	delam	58	0	100	-	61	1.21
Dissolvan15011 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	70	1.06
Dissolvan-4795 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	cmf	58	0	100	-	73	1.01
Dissolvan-4397 (Germ)	SD	30	47	0,15	cmf	58	0	100	-	96	0.77
IKHLAS-1 PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	14	5.3
IKHLAS-3 PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	21	3.5
IKHLAS-9 PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	24	3.1
IKHLAS-21PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	26	2.8
IKHLAS-26PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	17	4.3
IKHLAS-32PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	30	2.5
IKHLAS-36PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	31	2.4
IKHLAS-37PNS	SD	30	47	0,15	St DA	58	0	100	-	27	2.7
DEMTROL-2020(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	70	1.06
DEMTROL-2025(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	94	0.78
DEMTROL-2030(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	101	0.73
DEMTROL-3000(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	72	1.03
DEMTROL-3005(USA))	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	68	1.09
DEMTROL-3010(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	86	0.86
DEMTROL-3020(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	71	1.04
DEMTROL-4017(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	87	0.85
DEMTROL-4026(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	99	0.75
DEMTROL-4110(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	82	0.90
DEMTROL-4115(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	81	0.91
DEMTROL-4120(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	88	0.84
DEMTROL-5030(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	94	0.79
DEMTROL-5050(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	78	0.95
DEMTROL-5130(USA))	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	85	0.87
DEMTROL-5150(USA)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	90	0.82
DMO-080041 (USA, BH)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	76	0.97
DMO-86520 (USA, BH)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	74	1.00
DMO-86334 (USA, BH)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	71	1.04
Randem-2208 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	66	1.12
Randem-2210 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	79	0.94
Randem-2219 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	119	0.62
Randem-2224 (USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	124	0.59
Randem-2226 USA RN)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	114	0.65
E-401(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	95	0.78

E-402(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	90	0.82
E-403(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	103	0.72
E-404(Chin com-y 400)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	83	0.89
E-501(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	98	0.75
E-502(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	79	0.94
E-503(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	116	0.64
E-504(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	85	0.87
E-505(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	92	0.80
E-506(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	83	0.89
E-507(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	102	0.72
E-508(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	91	0.81
E-509(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	95	0.78
E-510(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	76	0.97
E-511(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	73	1.01
E-512(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	68	1.09
E-513(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	65	1.14
E-514(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	62	1.19
E-515(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	80	0.92
E-516(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	93	0.79
E-517(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	104	0.71
E-518(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	91	0.81
E-519(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	97	0.76
E-520(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	110	0.67
E-521(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	107	0.69
E-522(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	104	0.71
E-523(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	75	0.98
E-524(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	72	1.03
E-525(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	96	0.77
E-526(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	101	0.73
E-527(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	95	0.78
E-528(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	118	0.63
E-529(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	123	0.60
E-530(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	92	0.80
E-531(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	86	0.86
E-532(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	75	0.98
E-533(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	96	0.77
E-534(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	69	1.07

500)											
E-535(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	118	0.63
E-536(Chin com-y 500)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	75	0.98
E-602(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	54	1.37
E-603(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	85	0.87
E-607(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	73	1.01
E-610(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	86	0.86
E-611(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	77	0.96
E-612(Chin com-y 600)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	80	0.92
Control	-	-	47	0,15	-	58	4.0	93.1	-	93	0.79
Randem-2203 (BD)	SD	30	47	0,15	Stable	58	0	100	-	74 (BD)	-

Notes: dem. effic – demulsifier efficiency; Sc, g/t – specific consumption of demulsifiers; T_d – demulsification temperature; τ , hours - is the settling time of the bottle tests in a water bath at T_d ; Dem. stab – demulsifier stability; Con. of water, % - concentration of water in oil; init-l W_i – initial water; res-l W_r – residual water; D_d – degree of demulsification, $D_d = [(W_i - W_r) / W_i] \cdot 100$, %; DEID - destruction efficiency of inverse emulsions; EDIERBD - the effectiveness of the destruction of inverse emulsions relative to the base demulsifier. $EDIERBD = W_{rbd} / W_{rtd}$, (at times) W_{rbd} – residual water in the case of base demulsifier, W_{rtd} - residual water in the case of test demulsifier; ROCW - residual oil concentration in water, mg/dm^3 ; DEDERBD - destruction efficiency of direct emulsions relative to the base demulsifier, $DEDERBD = ROCW (BD) / ROCW (TD)$, bd - base demulsifier, td – test demulsifier; in expl – in exploitation; AOP – annual oil production per field, t; PNS – polynanostructured; St – stable; DA – desuspensifier ability; ρ - oil density, kg/m^3 ; T_{pp} – pour point of oil; ves – visco - elastic systems; hlws – high level of water solubility; delam – delamination; cmf – a curd mass is formed; SD – super demulsifier: $D_d = 99.8 - 100\%$; HED – highly effective demulsifier: $D_d = 99.0 - 99.8\%$; ED – effective demulsifier: $D_d = 97.0 - 99.0\%$; WD – weak demulsifier: $D_d = 80.0 - 97.0\%$; VWD – very weak demulsifier: $D_d =$ up to 80.0%.

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